

Performance Study of Cement Concrete Containing Natural Zeolite Powder and Glass Powder as Partial Replacement of Cement

¹Gopichand Gatti, ²Rahul Kumar Singh, ³V Pavan Kumar

¹P.G. Scholar, Department of Civil Engineering, Bonam Venkata Chalamayya Engineering College (Autonomous), Odalarevu, Andhra Pradesh, India. gatti.gopichand@gmail.com

²Assistant Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, Bonam Venkata Chalamayya Engineering College (Autonomous), Odalarevu, Andhra Pradesh, India. rahulkumarsingh238@gmail.com

³Assistant Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, Bonam Venkata Chalamayya Engineering College (Autonomous), Odalarevu, Andhra Pradesh, India. pavankumar.bvce@bvcgroup.in

Abstract: Concrete, as a fundamental construction material, is constantly evolving to enhance its performance and sustainability. This study explores the effects of incorporating natural zeolite powder and glass powder as partial replacements for cement in M50 grade concrete. The experimental investigation evaluates the compressive, split tensile, and flexural strengths of concrete specimens at 7, 14, and 28 days. Concrete mixtures containing various proportions of zeolite powder (10%, 20%, 30%) and glass powder (10%, 20%, 30%), both individually and in combination, were prepared and tested. Results indicate that the inclusion of zeolite and glass powders positively influences the strength properties of concrete, with certain mixes outperforming conventional concrete. The analysis of experimental data provides insights into the strength enhancement mechanisms and underscores the potential of these supplementary materials to improve the durability and sustainability of concrete structures. These findings contribute to the development of eco-friendly and high-performance concrete, advancing the field of construction materials engineering.

Keywords: Durability Properties, Glass powder, Environmental benefits, Mechanical Properties, Zeolite Powder.

1 INTRODUCTION

Concrete is the backbone of modern construction, valued for its versatility, strength, and cost-effectiveness. However, the production of traditional Portland cement, a critical component of concrete, has significant environmental drawbacks. Cement manufacturing is energy-intensive and releases substantial greenhouse gases, contributing to climate change. Additionally, the extraction of raw materials like limestone and clay depletes natural resources and impacts ecosystems. In response to these challenges, the construction industry is increasingly adopting sustainable practices, including the use of alternative materials to reduce concrete's environmental footprint. Supplementary Cementitious Materials (SCMs) and various additives have emerged as promising solutions, as they can reduce the need for cement while preserving concrete's durability and performance.

Zeolites, often referred to as "nature's molecular sieves," are aluminosilicate minerals known for their unique crystalline structures. With high surface area, uniform pore size, and strong ion exchange capabilities, zeolites are utilized in diverse industrial applications. Originally recognized in scientific research, these minerals are now finding applications in fields such as environmental remediation, agriculture, and construction materials, where they hold the potential for improving concrete properties.

Fig. 1 Natural Zeolite Material

Fig. 2 Zeolite Powder

Glass, a material long celebrated for its transparency and strength, has been widely used in architecture and design. However, its production is energy-intensive, and waste glass often ends up in landfills, posing environmental concerns. To address this issue, researchers are investigating methods to repurpose waste glass as a sustainable material in concrete production. Ground into fine particles, glass powder can serve as a partial replacement for cement, potentially reducing the concrete industry's environmental impact while maintaining material performance.

Fig. 3 Glass Powder

Objectives of the current research are given below.

- Analyze the physical, chemical, and pozzolanic characteristics of natural zeolite powder and glass powder to assess their effectiveness as alternatives to traditional cement.
- Investigate the properties of fresh and hardened concrete mixes incorporating various ratios of zeolite and glass powders, with a focus on workability, setting time, and early strength development.
- Evaluate the mechanical properties of concrete containing zeolite and glass powders, including compressive strength, flexural strength, and tensile strength.
- Examine the environmental impacts and economic feasibility of using zeolite and glass powders in concrete, considering factors such as energy consumption, carbon emissions, material costs, and waste reduction potential.
- Provide insights and recommendations for optimizing the use of natural zeolite powder and glass powder in concrete formulations, promoting sustainable practices and enhancing construction material performance.

2 LITERATURE SURVEY

Natural zeolite has emerged as an efficient supplementary cementitious material, offering benefits such as improved durability and reduced carbon emissions in concrete production. Shekarchi et al. [1] provided a comprehensive review of the properties and applications of natural zeolite, showing its potential to improve the strength, workability, and sustainability of concrete. Kriptavičius et al. [2] explored the combination of natural zeolite and glass powder as partial replacements for cement, demonstrating improved hydration and mechanical properties, along with reduced porosity. Similarly, Rudžionis et al. [3] found that incorporating natural zeolite in cementitious composites not only enhanced their strength but also allowed for the absorption of heavy metals, further underscoring the material's environmental benefits.

Santhosh et al. [4] examined the advancement of concrete by partially replacing cement with zeolite and fine aggregates with glass powder, highlighting the material's role in improving concrete strength and reducing its carbon footprint. Kriptavičius et al. [5] expanded on this by investigating the combined effects of natural zeolite and ground glass on the durability of concrete, with findings showing improved resistance to chloride migration and freeze-thaw cycles.

Al-Khazaleh and Kumar [6] optimized the use of natural zeolite and iron ore tailings as admixtures, improving both the mechanical properties and durability of concrete when replacing portions of cement and sand. Yu et al. [7] explored the effects of high volumes of zeolite powder in concrete, focusing on strength development and microstructure. Their results showed that zeolite improves long-term compressive strength and reduces porosity, with the 20% zeolite replacement level yielding optimal results. Alexa-Stratulat et al. [8] conducted a review of natural zeolites in cement-based materials, finding that while zeolite improves durability and strength, its slow pozzolanic reaction may reduce early-age strength. Bameri et al. [9] studied eco-friendly concrete containing zeolite, silica fume, waste glass powder, and ground granulated blast furnace slag, showing enhanced resistance to chemical attacks and improved mechanical properties.

Zandi and Rezaei [10] investigated the use of fly ash, zeolite powder, and glass fiber in lightweight concrete beams made of scoria, finding improvements in flexural strength and reduced environmental impact. Sajedi and Jalilifar [11] studied recycled concrete with natural zeolite, showing that it improved mechanical properties such as compressive and tensile strength. Rao et al. [12] examined the use of quartz powder and eggshell powder as partial replacements for cement, showing that both materials enhance the compressive, tensile, and flexural strength of concrete.

Anitha et al. [13] explored the use of Alccofine 1203 as a cement replacement, showing that a 10% replacement significantly improves the compressive strength and durability of concrete. Rajesh et al. [14] studied ceramic insulator waste (CIW) as a partial replacement for coarse aggregates, showing that up to 4% replacement improved the mechanical properties of concrete, although higher replacement levels reduced strength. Finally, Bharathi et al. [15] investigated the use of oil palm shell (OPS) and manufactured sand (M Sand) as replacements for coarse and fine aggregates, respectively, in concrete exposed to high temperatures. Their findings revealed that these replacements improved the concrete's strength and sustainability. Lastly, Mani et al. [16] examined the effects of pumice powder and polypropylene as partial replacements for cement, showing improvements in the tensile and compressive strength of concrete, demonstrating the potential of these materials to enhance the performance and sustainability of concrete structures.

3 MATERIALS USED

3.1 Cement

Cement serves as the primary binding component in concrete, providing strength and cohesiveness to the mixture. In this study, Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) of 53 grade from UltraTech Cement Company was utilized. This cement complies with IS 12269-1987 specifications. A summary of the physical properties of this cement is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Properties of Cement

S. No.	Property	Results
1	Specific Gravity	3.1
2	Initial setting time	36 min
3	Final setting time	320 min
4	Fineness (%)	94

3.2 Fine Aggregate

Fine aggregate plays a crucial role in concrete by filling voids within the coarse aggregate, thereby enhancing the overall compactness and strength of the concrete matrix. The properties of the fine aggregate used in this study are detailed in Table 2.

Table 2. Properties of Fine Aggregate

S. No.	Property	Test Results
1	Type	Normal sand
2	Specific gravity	2.68
3	Grading size	4.75mm – 0.075mm
4	Water absorption	0.6%
5	Fineness modulus	2.70
6	Bulk density	Loose state – 1378.82 kg/m ³ Compact State – 1544.67 kg/m ³

3.3 Coarse Aggregate

Coarse aggregate, with its larger particle size, provides bulk and stability to concrete mixes. This study employs crushed granite aggregate with a maximum particle size of 20 mm. Table 3 summarizes the properties of the coarse aggregate.

Table 3. Properties of Coarse Aggregate

S. No.	Particulars	Results
1	Type	Crushed stone
2	Specific gravity	2.66
3	Maximum size	20mm
4	Water absorption	0.5%
5	Fineness modulus	3.9
6	Bulk density	1688 kg/m ³

3.4 Zeolite Powder

Zeolite powder, when incorporated into concrete, can enhance the function of cement as a binder due to its similar building blocks. It is expected to improve the strength and quality of concrete compared to conventional mixes. The properties of zeolite powder are listed in Table 4.

Table 4. Properties of Zeolite Powder

S. No.	Properties	Results
1	Initial setting time	55 min
2	Final setting time	410 min
3	Particle size	5mm
4	Specific Gravity	2.8
5	Bulk Density	0.5-1.6g/cm ³
6	Fineness Modulus	3.3%
7	Water Absorption	1.5%

3.5 Glass Powder

Glass powder, as an additive, can enhance the mechanical properties of concrete through pozzolanic activity. The properties of glass powder used in this study are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5. Properties of Glass Powder

S. No.	Property	Results
1	Particle size	10-30 μ m
2	Specific Gravity	2.6
3	Water Absorption	0.06%
4	Bulk density	2-3 g/cm ³

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This section presents the findings from the experimental investigation, focusing on the strength characteristics of concrete specimens. Zeolite powder and glass powders were added in different proportions to produce as many as eight mixes out of which conventional concrete is the one. Tests were conducted to measure compressive strength, split tensile strength, flexural strength, and durability. The tests were performed at intervals of 7 days, 14 days, and 28 days to analyze the progression of strength over time.

Table 6. Mix Proportions

Mix Ratio	Abbreviation
Conventional Concrete	MIX 1
10% Zeolite Powder	MIX 2
20% Zeolite Powder	MIX 3
10% Glass Powder	MIX 4
20% Glass Powder	MIX 5
10% Zeolite & Glass Powder	MIX 6
20% Zeolite & Glass Powder	MIX 7
30% Zeolite & Glass Powder	MIX 8

4.1 Slump Test

The slump test was performed to evaluate the workability of the concrete mixes. Results are depicted in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 Slump Test Results

4.2 Compressive Strength Test

Concrete cubes measuring 150 mm x 150 mm x 150 mm were tested for compressive strength using a 2000 kN capacity compression testing machine. Measurements were taken on 7 days, 14 days, and 28 days. Results are displayed in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 Compressive Strength Results

Among all specimens, the mix containing 20% zeolite powder, and 20% glass powder (MIX 7) demonstrated the highest compressive strength. This highlights the substantial impact of these additives on higher concentrations.

4.3 Split Tensile Strength

The split tensile strength test provides insight into the tensile performance of the concrete specimens, which is crucial for assessing crack formation resistance. The results are shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6 Split Tensile Test Results

The results indicate that MIX 7 exhibited the highest tensile strength, reaching approximately 11.8 MPa, while conventional concrete (MIX 1) showed the lowest tensile strength at around 9.9 MPa.

4.4 Flexural Strength Test

Flexural strength is essential for applications involving bending or flexing loads. The results of the flexural strength test are presented in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 Flexural Strength Results

The 20% zeolite and glass powder mix (MIX 7) achieved the highest flexural strength, demonstrating the positive synergy of combining these materials at higher concentrations.

4.5 Water Permeability Test

The water permeability test results, as shown in Fig. 8, reveal a correlation between the inclusion of zeolite and glass powder and reduced water permeability. Increasing additive concentration led to decreased permeability, indicating improved durability.

Fig. 8 Water Permeability Results

4.6 Acid Curing Test

The acid curing test results, displayed in Fig. 9, indicate trends similar to those observed under normal water curing conditions. Compressive strength varied based on the curing environment and additive concentrations, with the 20% zeolite and glass powder mix (MIX 7) again demonstrating optimum strength.

Fig. 9 Acid Curing Results

4.7 Water Absorption Test

Water absorption tests revealed that specimens containing mineral additives exhibited higher water absorption than control specimens after 28 days of curing. Despite this increase in water absorption, the mechanical strength of these specimens varied, as shown in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10 Water Absorption Results

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study provides a detailed examination of concrete strength properties, including compressive strength, split tensile strength, and flexural strength, over curing periods of 7, 14, and 28 days. Results reveal a significant positive correlation between the inclusion of zeolite and glass powder additives and enhanced compressive strength, highlighting their potential as effective reinforcement components in concrete mixes. The superior performance of the mix containing a combined 20% concentration of zeolite and glass powder (MIX 7) suggests a synergistic effect, underscoring the importance of carefully adjusting additive proportions to achieve optimal results. Notably, this mix consistently outperformed other specimens across all curing periods in both split tensile and flexural strength tests. Furthermore, increased proportions of zeolite and glass powder were associated with reduced permeability, indicating enhanced durability. However, water absorption tests—conducted through immersion and open porosity—showed that specimens with partial cement replacement by these mineral materials had higher water absorption compared to control specimens, despite differing mechanical strength outcomes. These findings underscore the potential of natural zeolite powder and glass powder as sustainable and effective additives in concrete, contributing valuable insights for future optimization in construction applications.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to sincerely thank the Department of Civil Engineering, Bonam Venkata Chalamayya Engineering College (Autonomous), Odalarevu, for providing invaluable support throughout this research for the access to the necessary hardware and equipment, which greatly contributed to the successful completion of this research.

FUNDING INFORMATION

This research received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

ETHICS STATEMENT

This study did not involve human or animal subjects and, therefore, did not require ethical approval.

STATEMENT OF CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no conflicts of interest related to this study.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Shekarchi, B. Ahmadi, F. Azarhomayun, B. Shafei, and M. Kioumars, "Natural zeolite as a supplementary cementitious material – A holistic review of main properties and applications," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 409, p. 133766, Oct. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2023.133766.
- [2] D. Kriptavičius, G. Girskas, and G. Skripkiūnas, "Use of natural zeolite and glass powder mixture as partial replacement of portland cement: The effect on hydration, properties and porosity," *Materials*, vol. 15, no. 12, p. 4219, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.3390/ma15124219.
- [3] Ž. Rudžionis *et al.*, "Natural zeolite powder in cementitious composites and its application as heavy metal absorbents," *Journal of Building Engineering*, vol. 43, p. 103085, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.job.2021.103085.

- [4] A. Santhosh, A. Shinoji, A. Jayakumar, G. L. P. J, and A. G. Raj, “Advancement of Concrete by Partially Replacing Cement by Zeolite & Fine Aggregate by Glass Powder,” *E3S Web of Conferences*, vol. 529, p. 01037, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.1051/e3sconf/202452901037.
- [5] D. Kriptavičius, G. Girskas, E. Ivanauskas, and A. Korjakins, “Complex Effect of Portland Cement Modified with Natural Zeolite and Ground Glass Mixture on Durability Properties of Concrete,” *Buildings*, vol. 13, no. 10, p. 2576, Oct. 2023, doi: 10.3390/buildings13102576.
- [6] M. Al-Khazaleh and P. K. Kumar, “Optimization studies of iron ore tailings powder and natural zeolite as concrete admixtures,” *Civil Engineering Journal*, vol. 9, no. 12, pp. 3075–3091, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.28991/cej-2023-09-12-08.
- [7] Z. Yu, W. Yang, P. Zhan, X. Liu, and D. Chen, “Strengths, microstructure and nanomechanical properties of concrete containing high volume of zeolite powder,” *Materials*, vol. 13, no. 18, p. 4191, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.3390/ma13184191.
- [8] S.-M. Alexa-Stratulat *et al.*, “The Use of Natural Zeolites in Cement-Based Construction Materials—A State of the Art review,” *Coatings*, vol. 14, no. 1, p. 18, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.3390/coatings14010018.
- [9] M. Bameri, S. Rashidi, M. Mohammadhasani, M. Maghsoudi, H. Madani, and F. Rahmani, “Evaluation of mechanical and durability properties of Eco-Friendly concrete containing silica fume, waste glass powder, and ground granulated blast furnace SLAG,” *Advances in Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 2022, pp. 1–22, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1155/2022/2730391.
- [10] Y. Zandi and A. Rezaei, “Evaluation of the effect of fly ash and zeolite powder and glass fiber on flexural behavior of structural lightweight beams made of Scoria,” *DOAJ (DOAJ: Directory of Open Access Journals)*, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.22065/jsce.2018.129538.1549.
- [11] F. Sajedi and H. Jalilifar, “Investigation on mechanical properties of recycled concrete containing natural zeolite,” *Neliti*, Mar. 01, 2017. <https://www.neliti.com/publications/257500/investigation-on-mechanical-properties-of-recycled-concrete-containing-natural-z>
- [12] Allu Taraka Rama Rao, Ravi Kumar, Chandra Mouli V.S.A, “Performance Study of Plain cement concrete containing quartz powder and eggshell powder as partial replacement of cement,” *International Journal of Emerging Research in Engineering, Science, and Management*, vol. 3, issue 3, pp. 59-69, July-Sep 2024, doi: 10.58482/ijeresm.v3i3.10.
- [13] Vipparthi Anitha, P. Gnanamoorthy, Ch. Sivanarayana, “Enhancing the Performance and Durability of M35 Grade Concrete with Alccofine 1203,” *International Journal of Emerging Research in Engineering, Science, and Management*, vol. 3, issue 4, pp. 01-10, Oct-Dec 2024, doi: 10.58482/ijeresm.v3i4.1.
- [14] Seelam Rajesh, K. Sai Anitha, Ch. Sivanarayana, “Impact of Ceramic Insulator Waste as Partial Replacement of Coarse Aggregate in Concrete: An Experimental Study and Evaluation of Mechanical Properties,” *International Journal of Emerging Research in Engineering, Science, and Management*, vol. 3, issue 4, pp. 11-19, Oct-Dec 2024, doi: 10.58482/ijeresm.v3i4.2.
- [15] Vakula Bharathi Geddam, Ch. Sivanarayana, P. Gnanamoorthy, “An Experimental Investigation on Partial Replacement of Oil Palm Shell as Coarse Aggregate and M Sand as Fine Aggregate with Elevated Temperature,” *International Journal of Emerging Research in Engineering, Science, and Management*, vol. 3, issue 4, pp. 20-27, Oct-Dec 2024, doi: 10.58482/ijeresm.v3i4.3.
- [16] Divya Mani Palnati, Nageswara Rao Pasupuleti, P Chandra Mouli V.S.A., “Evaluation of the Performance of Plain Cement Concrete with Partial Replacement of Cement by Natural Pumice Powder and Polypropylene,” *International Journal of Emerging Research in Engineering, Science, and Management*, vol. 3, issue 4, pp. 37-46, Oct-Dec 2024, doi: 10.58482/ijeresm.v3i4.6.